

PhD. Student. Emir Halabi

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4592-3760>

Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi, İ.İ.B.F., İktisat Bölümü, Kahramanmaraş / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/03gn5cg19>

Doç. Dr. Mustafa Baylan

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8604-4634>

Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi, İ.İ.B.F., İktisat Bölümü, Kahramanmaraş / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/03gn5cg19>

Trade Relations Between Türkiye and The MENA Region in The Context of The Arab Spring Revolutions

Türkiye ile MENA Bölgesi Arasındaki Ticaret, Arap Baharı Devrimleri Işığında

ABSTRACT

Given the strategic significance of the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) on the global stage, particularly in relation to Turkey's established relationships and ongoing developments within the region, this paper aims to highlight the trade dynamics between Turkey and MENA in the context of the Arab Spring revolutions. Utilizing both historical and descriptive analytical methodologies, as well as quantitative approaches, the study analyzes Turkish foreign trade data to identify key indicators that reflect the impact of the Arab Spring on trade dynamics. The findings indicate that the Arab Spring revolutions have influenced the trade volume between Turkey and the MENA region post-2012, with varying effects observed across different countries. While Turkey's trade balance with the MENA region remains more favorable compared to other regions, the growth rate of trade volume with MENA has been slower than that with other regions.

Keywords: Foreign Trade, Arab Spring, Turkey, MENA Region

ÖZET

Orta Doğu ve Kuzey Afrika'nın (MENA) küresel siyasetteki stratejik önemi, özellikle Türkiye'nin bölgedeki mevcut ilişkileri ve devam eden gelişmeler ışığında değerlendirildiğinde, bu çalışmanın amacı Arap Baharı devrimleri bağlamında Türkiye ile MENA arasındaki ticaret dinamiklerini ortaya koymaktır. Çalışma, tarihsel ve tanımlayıcı analitik metodolojilerin yanı sıra nicel yaklaşımları kullanarak, Arap Baharı'nın ticaret dinamikleri üzerindeki etkisini yansıtan temel göstergeleri belirlemek için Türk dış ticaret verilerini analiz etmektedir. Elde edilen bulgular, Arap Baharı devrimlerinin 2012 sonrasındaki dönemde Türkiye ile MENA bölgesi arasındaki ticaret hacmini etkilediğini, ancak farklı ülkelerde değişken etkilerin gözlemlendiğini ortaya koymaktadır. Türkiye'nin MENA bölgesi ile olan ticaret dengesi, diğer bölgelere kıyasla daha elverişli bir durum sergilerken, MENA ile ticaret hacminin büyüme oranı, diğer bölgelerle karşılaştırıldığında daha yavaş bir seyir izlemektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Dış Ticaret, Arap Baharı, Türkiye, MENA Bölgesi.

1. INTRODUCTION

As stated by Krugman, foreign trade serves as a cornerstone of the global economy, acting as a key sector that attracts foreign direct investment and promotes the adoption of modern technologies, significantly contributing to the GDP of nations (Mansouri, 2022: 93). A nation's foreign trade reflects its economic policies, illustrating their effectiveness and direction. It is essential for generating foreign exchange, promoting the growth of domestic economies, and contributing to the overall economic framework. This highlights its significant importance to countries around the globe.

Foreign trade has historically been a fundamental aspect of external economic relations. Its impact on economic development has significantly increased, particularly following World War II. In recent decades, advancements in foreign trade have become a crucial factor contributing to the growth of both national and global economies (Jeníček & Krepl, 2009: 211). Recognizing the crucial role that trade plays in shaping the national economy, countries have implemented a variety of strategies to enhance their foreign trade capabilities. These initiatives include creating a supportive environment for domestic producers, promoting increased production, providing incentives to attract investment, offering support for exports, actively participating in regional and global organizations, and securing trade agreements. Furthermore, additional measures have been introduced to stimulate trade growth.

Turkish foreign policy has strategically prioritized the protection of the country's regional and global interests while fostering an environment that supports peace and sustainable development. This objective has been pursued through a range of political, economic, humanitarian, and cultural initiatives. Additionally, Turkey has placed significant emphasis on enhancing its political and economic relationships and on cultivating comprehensive partnerships and close collaboration with nations worldwide (Legamart, 02.10.2024: legamart.com).

The MENA region is of great global importance due to its important location at the center of the world. Its diverse geography and control over critical waterways, including the Bab al-Mandab Strait, Bab al-Salam Strait, Suez Canal, and Strait of Gibraltar, make it a central hub for international trade. Furthermore, the region is rich in natural and human resources, has significant energy reserves, and features a large market. Collectively, these factors have solidified MENA as a vital focus for economic interests and global investment.

Turkey has adopted the concept of strategic depth, drawing upon its rich history and distinctive geographical position. This approach underscores the importance of cultivating relationships with nations that have historical and geographical ties to Turkey, with the goal of enhancing shared interests and creating a solid foundation for collaboration and dialogue (Davutoğlu, 2012b). Turkey's relationship with the MENA region is grounded in a rich shared history, along with significant religious, cultural, and traditional ties. This foundation has progressively evolved into an emphasis on strengthening partnerships. In recent years, Turkey has enhanced its initiatives to deepen these connections, resulting in a series of successful agreements and collaborative projects. These efforts have notably contributed to a significant increase in trade volumes, highlighting the expanding economic synergy between Turkey and the MENA countries.

The term "Arab Spring" describes a sequence of mass uprisings and popular protests that sought to challenge authoritarian regimes, originating in Tunisia in late 2010 and expanding to several Arab nations, including Egypt, Libya, Syria, Yemen, and Bahrain (Campante & Chor, 2012: 167). These revolutionary movements led to significant shifts in political power and changes in governance across various countries. Consequently, this has had profound humanitarian repercussions, including considerable loss of life and the displacement of numerous individuals.

This movement has been instrumental in promoting democratic transition processes within the region. It was driven by citizens' increasing demands for greater freedom of expression, efforts to address ongoing social and economic inequalities, and the pursuit of improved living standards (Öncel & Malik, 2015: 17). Additionally, the upheavals fostered the development of new alliances and intensified rivalries, creating a complex network of competing interests among countries in the region. These evolving dynamics continue to have a lasting influence on political relationships and trade activities across the area.

Turkey has experienced the effects of developments in the MENA region, which have significantly influenced its political and economic relationships with various countries in the area. These adjustments have significantly influenced Turkey's foreign trade dynamics and its overall trade volume with these countries. Consequently, it is essential to examine how the unfolding dynamics of the Arab Spring have influenced and redefined trade relations between Turkey and MENA countries. This research topic is motivated by several key factors: the significant role of foreign trade in national economies, the profound consequences of the Arab Spring revolutions and their enduring effects on Turkey, the global and regional importance of the MENA region—especially for Turkey—and the identified gap in academic discourse regarding the ramifications of the Arab Spring on Turkey's foreign trade relations with MENA countries. This research holds significant importance as it examines a critical component of the national economy: the foreign trade sector. It explores a strategically vital region that plays a crucial role in influencing global trade dynamics, particularly for Turkey. Furthermore, the study evaluates a key variable that has substantial implications for both the overall Turkish economy and its foreign trade activities.

This study's primary hypothesis posits that the Arab Spring revolutions have influenced trade dynamics between Turkey and MENA countries. Additionally, a secondary hypothesis suggests that this influence has had a negative effect, resulting in a decrease in trade volumes between Turkey and the region. The MENA region represents a significant market opportunity for Turkey, providing considerable potential to enhance its presence in global trade and increase the international visibility of Turkish products. Accordingly, this research aims to validate both the primary and secondary hypotheses by analyzing the trade dynamics between Turkey and the MENA region within the framework of the Arab Spring uprisings.

This study utilizes a descriptive, analytical, and historical methodology to investigate the evolution of the Arab Spring and the trade dynamics between Turkey and the MENA region. The research includes an examination of trade agreements established between Turkey and MENA countries, as well as Turkish foreign trade statistics from 2000 to 2020. Additionally, Turkey's foreign trade performance will be assessed in comparison to seven

distinct geographical regions. The collected data will be systematically analyzed to derive key insights into the impact of the Arab Spring's influence on trade volumes with MENA countries. In Section Four, a quantitative approach will be employed to conduct econometric analysis of trade flows between Turkey and MENA nations. Statistical data on Turkish foreign trade will be obtained from World Bank databases, and regional trade data will be sourced from the World Integrated Trade Solutions (WITS) platform. Additionally, information regarding trade agreements between Turkey and MENA countries will be collected from official resources provided by the Turkish Ministry of Foreign Trade.

To effectively address the research question and thoroughly evaluate the proposed hypotheses, this study is structured into four key sections, in addition to the introduction. The first section reviews relevant literature on the research topic. The second section explores the historical contexts during the Arab Spring uprisings. The third section analyzes trade dynamics between Turkey and the MENA region. Finally, the fourth section features an econometric analysis of trade flows between Turkey and MENA countries. The study concludes with a summary of the principal findings and outlines the final conclusions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Arab Spring has attracted considerable attention, resulting in a multitude of studies and research initiatives that analyze its diverse impacts across several areas, including corruption, economic growth, foreign investment, and trade in services. This section presents a curated selection of research that explores the impact of the Arab Spring various dimensions such as trade, economic growth, corruption, and related fields.

The research conducted by AlShammari, Willoughby and Behbahan in 2023 highlights the adverse effects of political instability stemming from the Arab Spring revolutions on foreign direct investment. Additionally, Kırşanlı (2023) identified the detrimental impact of corruption associated with these revolutions on economic growth. His analysis suggests that a one-unit increase in corruption, as measured by global governance indicators, correlates with a decline in economic growth rates of between 1.64 and 2.98 percentage points. Karim (2021) concludes that the economic growth of the Middle East was more adversely affected by the Arab Spring than by the global financial crisis. The research conducted by Echevarría and García-Enríquez (2020) found that between 2011 and 2017, the Arab Spring uprising in Egypt led to a cumulative decrease in the rate of growth for real GDP per capita by 12.04%. The estimated cumulative losses in real GDP per capita amounted to approximately \$6,279.70, while total losses in real GDP during that period were estimated at around \$582.5 billion. Research conducted by Mamdouh Abdel Wahid and Mohamed Saeed Abdel M (2020) emphasizes the crucial impact of neglecting social dimensions in development policies within Arab nations, especially in Egypt. This oversight has contributed to increased poverty and unemployment, weakening equitable income and wealth distribution and exacerbating disparities in the benefits of development initiatives. As a result, the economic and social circumstances of various groups have experienced significant deterioration. These shortcomings in promoting social justice are identified as key factors that contributed in relation to the emergence of the Arab Spring uprisings. Arayssi, M., Fakhri, A., & Haimoun, N. (2019) demonstrated that the Arab Spring uprisings had a distinct negative effect on the economic growth rates of countries in the MENA region. A study conducted by Hraiba, Ganić and Branković in 2019 indicated a negative relationship observed in the context of the Arab Spring uprisings and foreign direct investment flows. The findings revealed that countries in North Africa experienced a more significant impact when contrasted with counterparts in the Middle East. A research study conducted by Masoud et al. (2019) provided valuable insights into the structural factors influencing the increase of protests in 19 Arab League countries from 1990 to 2011. The findings revealed that protests were notably more intense in nations experiencing high inflation, rising levels of corruption, limited freedoms, and higher rates of internet and mobile phone usage. Furthermore, the study indicated that protests were more common in countries characterized by partial democracies and political systems that rely on factional competition. Notably, the research challenged the widely held belief that the 2011 wave of protests was closely linked to a growing youth population, as it found no substantial evidence to support this idea. In 2019, Mustafa Kahveci highlighted the significant adverse effects of the post-Arab Spring period on business activities between Turkey and the countries across the MENA regions. Research conducted by AlOtean in 2018 indicated that the Arab Spring revolutions had adverse effects on the economy of the Arab region, particularly evidenced by a substantial decline in foreign direct investment and its subsequent withdrawal from the area. Research conducted by Veninga and Ihle (2018) provides compelling evidence of a significant decline in wheat demand in Egypt during the latter half of 2011. This downturn is primarily linked to the extensive and ongoing political turmoil that followed the occurrences of the Arab Spring. A study conducted by Button, Martini and Scotti in 2016 provided limited evidence indicating a short-term negative effects of the Arab Spring on air service trade between certain Middle Eastern and North African nations. Nonetheless, the study also observed diverse effects, with some cases resulting in positive outcomes. A 2016 study conducted by E. Cohen indicated that the Syrian revolution during the Arab Spring had considerable negative impacts on the nation's economy and

unemployment rates. The findings emphasize that Syria experienced a more severe economic downturn, primarily due to increased security instability, compared to the situations noted in Egypt and Libya. Research conducted by Matta, S., Appleton, S., and Bleaney, M. (2016) analyzed Tunisia's economic trajectory following the events of the Arab Spring. The study revealed significant GDP losses of 5.5% in 2011, 5.1% in 2012, and 6.4% in 2013. The findings emphasized that investment was the most negatively impacted factor, which notably contributed to the challenges faced by the Tunisian economy during this period. A study conducted by Öncel & Malik in 2015 revealed that Turkish trade faced a decline after the emergence of the Arab Spring revolutions. However, this decline was subsequently followed by an improvement, which was linked to changes in political relations between Turkey and the affected countries. Research conducted by Hacıoğlu and Saylan in 2014 aimed to assess the impact of the Arab Spring on the tourism sector. The findings suggest that Turkey and certain Arab nations successfully capitalized on the political and social unrest as a strategic opportunity. In contrast, the majority of the Arab region faced adverse outcomes, which were evidenced by a significant decline in tourist arrivals and a corresponding decrease in overall tourism-related revenue. Research conducted by Abdelbaki, Hisham (2013) identified political instability as the primary factor influencing stock market performance, followed by economic instability as the second most significant element. The study established a clear relationship between the extent of participation in protests and sit-ins, as well as their specific demands, and the fluctuations of the Egyptian pound's exchange rate against the US dollar, along with the key stock market indices, EGX30 and EGX70.

3. THE ARAB SPRING: AN OVERVIEW AND CONTEXT

The "Arab Spring" refers to a significant wave of socio-political changes characterized by protests, revolutions, and civil unrest directed against ruling authorities, which began in late 2010 across several Arab countries. This pivotal period led to the overthrow of longstanding governments in Egypt, Tunisia, Yemen and Libya, while civil uprisings in Bahrain and Syria. In Syria, the protests escalated into a prolonged civil conflict, intensifying sectarian tensions in neighboring Lebanon. Additionally, numerous other nations in the Arab region, including Algeria, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Morocco, and Sudan, experienced widespread demonstrations that expressed profound public dissatisfaction with their leadership. Smaller-scale protests were also observed in countries such as Mauritania, Oman, Saudi Arabia, and minority regions of Iran, highlighting the broader regional implications of this movement (El Faith, 2015: 121-122).

3.1. Historical Background of the Arab Spring

The revolutions of the Arab Spring began on December 17, 2010, following a tragic event involving Mohamed Bouazizi, a young Tunisian university graduate who self-immolated. This incident coincided with the release of classified U.S. diplomatic cables by WikiLeaks, which revealed significant issues within the Tunisian regime. These events catalyzed a widespread series of protests across Tunisia, fueled by calls for political reform, social justice, and economic advancement (Ardıç, 2012, 9). The unrest ultimately led to the downfall of the government. Inspired by Tunisia's example, the revolutionary momentum quickly spread to countries such as Egypt and Libya, leading to comparable changes in leadership. The movement further expanded to Syria, Yemen, and Bahrain, culminating in significant demonstrations and escalating into prolonged conflicts in Syria and Yemen (Öncel & Malik, 2015: 18).

3.2. Factors Contributing Regarding the Arab Spring Uprisings

The factors contributing to the Arab Spring revolutions are multifaceted, with the most significant being:

- Years of diminished democratic participation, pervasive corruption, elevated unemployment rates, and growing class disparities, alongside the failure to tackle the pressing political, economic, and social challenges confronting the population (Khan, 2014: 1).
- The aspirations of emerging generations to create a society that ensures dignity, freedom, justice, and equality for all.
- The inability of authoritarian regimes to meet the demands and fulfill the aspirations of the people, particularly among the educated youth (Ardıç, 2012: 40).
- The intention of certain foreign nations to initiate political, economic, and demographic changes in the region while striving for their interests and objectives.
- The Internet and social media have been instrumental in enabling protesters to articulate their demands and raising global awareness of these revolutions. By documenting events and highlighting human rights violations, these platforms generated international pressure on the governments involved.

3.3. Consequences of the Arab Spring Movements

The Arab Spring revolutions have significantly transformed the political landscape in the MENA region, resulting in the overthrow of regimes in nations like Egypt, Tunisia, Libya and Yemen. This wave of change has also compelled other governments, including those in Jordan and Morocco, to implement reforms to address the demands of their citizens, while still maintaining their authority. However, the aftermath of these uprisings has left many economies in the region facing considerable challenges, particularly during the early stages of transition. These challenges include slow economic growth, high unemployment rates, ongoing political and social unrest, and a decline in security—factors that have collectively discouraged both domestic and international investment. Consequently, numerous countries are facing a more precarious economic and social landscape than they did before the Arab Spring. This precarious situation is largely a result of a strong emphasis on resolving political issues at the cost of economic concerns, leading to delays in essential economic reforms based on the belief that political stability must be prioritised. This perspective has overlooked the critical interdependence between political stability and economic resilience (Khan, 2014: 1). Additionally, the situation has led the engagement of global and regional powers in proxy conflicts, particularly in Syria and Yemen, which has redistributed influence and interests across the region.

World Bank data reveals a significant transformation in the economic trends of key Arab Spring countries, as evidenced by their Gross Domestic Product (GDP) movements. Notably, Syria has experienced a dramatic decline in its economic performance. Since 2012, Syria's GDP has fallen substantially, decreasing by approximately 82.16% over ten years—from \$67.54 billion in 2011 to only \$12.5 billion in 2020. In contrast, Tunisia experienced a modest economic recovery in the wake of the Arab Spring's initial upheaval, with GDP increasing from \$46.21 billion in 2010 to \$50.27 billion by 2014. However, this growth trend reversed, leading to a decline to \$41.91 billion in 2019. Libya's economic path has been marked by significant volatility. The country registered a steep GDP contraction in 2011, followed by a temporary recovery in 2012, after which a period of prolonged fluctuations ensued. By 2022, Libya's GDP had decreased to \$35.22 billion, a considerable drop from the \$75.38 billion recorded in 2010, reflecting an overall decrease of approximately 53.28%. Yemen initially saw economic growth, with GDP rising from \$30.91 billion in 2010 to a peak of \$43.23 billion in 2014. However, this positive trend was abruptly interrupted by a severe downturn starting in 2015; by 2018, Yemen's GDP had significantly declined to \$21.61 billion. In stark contrast to these trends, Egypt has exhibited a consistent trajectory of economic growth during the same period. Egypt's GDP increased from \$218.98 billion in 2010 to an impressive \$476.75 billion by 2022, indicating a growth rate of approximately 117.71%. This divergent economic path highlights the resilience and growth of the Egyptian economy compared to the other nations affected by the Arab Spring events.

Table 1: GDP (current (bn) US\$) Source: (World Bank data)

Year	Syrian	Tunisia	Libya	Egypt	Yemen
2010	61,39	46,21	75,38	218,98	30,91
2011	67,54	48,12	48,17	235,99	32,73
2012	43,19	47,31	92,54	279,12	35,4
2013	21,36	48,69	75,35	288,43	40,42
2014	21,5	50,27	57,37	305,6	43,23
2015	16,47	45,78	48,72	329,37	42,44
2016	12,6	44,36	49,91	332,44	31,32
2017	16,37	42,16	67,16	248,36	26,84
2018	21,5	42,69	76,69	262,59	21,61
2019	22,58	41,91	69,25	318,68	
2020	12,05	42,49	46,85	383,82	
2021	14,35	46,81	35,22	424,67	
2022	23,62	44,58	43,25	476,75	

4. TRADE DYNAMICS BETWEEN TURKEY AND THE MENA REGION

4.1. Turkish Policy Toward the MENA Region

Until the late 1980s, Turkey did not prioritize the enhancement of its relations with MENA countries. However, beginning in the early 1990s, there was a gradual shift toward fostering economic relations with certain regional nations. As the new millennium commenced, Turkey further expanded its connections with the Mediterranean countries (Falk, 2012: 1-2). The foreign policies implemented by Turkey since the onset of the twenty-first century, which focus on enhancing political relations with neighboring countries, have significantly contributed to the advancement of economic relations with nations in the Middle East and North Africa (Davutoğlu, 2008: 79-82).

Before the Arab Spring revolutions, Turkey maintained strong relationships with the authoritarian regimes in Tunisia, Libya, Egypt, and Syria, where shared interests served as a foundation for this cooperation. With the advent of these revolutions, Turkey encountered a combination of opportunities and challenges that reshaped its regional policies. In this context, Turkey took a proactive approach in supporting popular movements that opposed authoritarian governance from the outset, indicating a significant shift in its political stance (Davutoğlu, 2012a: 8). From this viewpoint, Turkish foreign policy has been oriented towards a vision that emphasizes the promotion of democratic transformation both within the country and throughout the region (Paul & Serek, 2011: 1).

Turkey recognizes the vital link between security and stability both within its borders and across the MENA region. To address this interconnected issue, Turkey is committed to supporting neighboring nations in enhancing their security and stability. Additionally, the country is dedicated to fostering strong bilateral relations with regional partners to promote mutual welfare and prosperity (Republic of Türkiye, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, n.d.).

4.2. The Economic Roots of The Rapprochement Between Turkey and The MENA Region

Turkey's economic advancements in the early 21st century have notably strengthened its relationships with countries in MENA region. World Bank data from 2015 indicates that Turkey achieved the highest GDP growth rate among OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) member countries from 2003 to 2013, with an impressive annual growth rate of 5%. This impressive performance positioned Turkey as the 18th largest economy in the world by 2013. Additionally, GDP per capita experienced significant growth, increasing from approximately \$4,278 in 2000 to around \$12,578 in 2013, which reflects a remarkable growth rate of 194 percent. Simultaneously, the volume of foreign trade expanded markedly, rising from about \$116 billion in 2000 to nearly \$503 billion in 2013, highlighting Turkey's active integration into global markets, a trend that is quantitatively illustrated in Table 2.

The MENA region has emerged as a significant alternative market for Turkey, particularly in the aftermath of 2008-2009, which resulted in an economic downturn in European Union countries and a subsequent decline in Turkish exports to Europe. Additionally, the ongoing challenges related to Turkey's EU accession negotiations have further motivated the country to enhance its trade relations with MENA nations (Sen and others, 2016:18). In the context of the improved relations with MENA countries, various initiatives have been implemented to promote trade. These include the signing of multiple free trade agreements, the establishment of preferential trade regimes, and the introduction of measures to facilitate the free movement of individuals, such as visa provisions and exemptions (Sen and others, 2016: 11).

Table 2: Turkish Foreign Trade Data (bn \$) **Source** (World bank data)

Year	Exports	Imports	Trade volume	Change in trade volume, base year 2000 (%)	GDP per capita (current US\$)	1Change in GDPPC, base 2000
2000	54,53	61,64	116,2	0,00%	4278,26	0,00%
2001	54,84	45,78	100,6	-13,39%	3100,46	-27,53%
2002	60,31	54,96	115,3	-0,77%	3640,76	-14,90%
2003	72,38	73,05	145,4	25,17%	4704,77	9,97%
2004	96,59	103	199,6	71,84%	6031,79	40,99%
2005	110,8	122,9	233,6	101,10%	7369,43	72,25%
2006	124,8	146,9	271,7	133,82%	8003,81	87,08%
2007	149,1	176,9	326	180,62%	9711,22	126,99%
2008	181,6	207,9	389,5	235,22%	10843,5	153,46%
2009	151,7	152	303,8	161,49%	9013	110,67%
2010	164,7	198,1	362,8	212,29%	10622,7	148,29%
2011	192,9	254,2	447,1	284,85%	11300,79	164,14%
2012	214,5	250,7	465,2	300,43%	11713,28	173,79%
2013	227,9	275,2	503,1	333,06%	12578,19	194,00%
2014	236,7	268,2	504,8	334,54%	12165,22	184,35%
2015	212	229,5	441,6	280,08%	11050	158,28%
2016	200,8	219,6	420,3	261,78%	10970,05	156,41%
2017	223,7	255,3	479	312,30%	10695,55	150,00%
2018	243,3	244,5	487,8	319,84%	9568,84	123,66%
2019	251,7	229,2	480,9	313,95%	9215,44	115,40%
2020	209,8	232,1	441,9	280,36%	8638,74	101,92%
2021	293,1	289,7	582,8	401,64%	9743,21	127,74%
2022	350	386,3	736,3	533,79%	10674,5	149,51%
2023	357,6	384,4	742	538,66%	12985,75	203,53%

¹ Change in GDP per capita, base year 2000 (%)

4.3. Trade Agreements Between Turkey and MENA Countries

According to information from the Turkish Ministry of Foreign Trade, Turkey has entered into 85 agreements with 18 countries in the MENA region. The initial agreement was established in 1972, while the most recent one occurred in 2021. Notably, 39% of these agreements were signed prior to the year 2000, whereas 61% were executed following this year. In relation to the Arab revolutions, 74% of the agreements were concluded before 2011, and 26% were finalized thereafter.

Figure 1: Percentage of Agreements Signed Between Turkey and MENA Countries by Years. **Source:** based on TCTB data.

Breaking down the agreements by decade, we observe that 8 agreements, or approximately 9%, were signed during the 1970s, with a similar number and percentage for the 1980s. The 1990s saw the signing of 16 agreements, this is 19% of the total. In the first decade of the 21st century, 28 agreements were concluded, representing 33% of the total agreements. In the subsequent decade, 22 agreements were signed, comprising 26% of the overall agreements. The remaining 4% of the agreements were executed after 2020 (TCTB, n.d.), as shown in Figure 1.

Upon reviewing the previous figure, it is evident that trade agreements between Turkey and the MENA countries commenced in the 1970s, indicating a lack of prior agreements and suggesting limited Turkish engagement with this region before that time. In the 1970s and 1980s, there was an emerging interest in the MENA countries, which is illustrated by the signing of only 16 agreements over a period of two decades. The significant interest in the MENA region began to materialize in the 1990s, marked by a significant rise in the quantity of trade agreements. This trend peaked in the 2000s, with 28 agreements signed during this decade, representing 33% of the total agreements executed. During the early years of the 2010s, although the number of signed trade agreements decreased compared to the preceding decade, it still exceeded the numbers from the 1990s.

The agreements established between Turkey and countries in the MENA region demonstrate a diverse range of focuses. Notably, the predominant categories include agreements aimed at avoiding double taxation and those for the mutual promotion and protection of investments, with each category comprising 16 agreements. This is followed by 11 economic cooperation agreements, 9 agreements related to economic and technical cooperation, 9 trade agreements, 7 free trade agreements, 5 agreements pertaining to economic, industrial, and technical cooperation, in addition to one agreement concerning a joint economic committee and a trade and economic partnership agreement.

Analyzing the earlier data, it becomes clear that the number of free trade agreements formed between Turkey and the MENA region remains comparatively limited when measured against the total number of MENA nations. This indicates that the level of rapprochement and trade exchange is still low and has not reached its potential. There are only seven signed free trade agreements, including a pending agreement with Syria and a finalized agreement with Jordan.

It is important to clarify that the agreements referenced do not encompass the arrangements established between Turkey and both Israel and Iran. Specifically, regarding the agreements made with Israel, there are six primary agreements: the mutual assistance agreement between customs administrations, the mutual encouragement and protection of investments agreement, the agreement to prevent double taxation and tax evasion, and the agreement on commercial, economic, industrial, technical, and scientific cooperation. Additionally, this list includes the free trade agreement signed in 1996 and the fourth session of the joint committee between Turkey and Israel that took place in 2009. In relation to the trade agreements with Iran, they are limited to two agreements: the first is the preferential trade agreement between Turkey and Iran, which was signed in 2014, and the second is the Turkish - Iranian memorandum of understanding in its twenty-seventh version, signed in 2019.

4.4. Trade Volume

According to Table 3, figure 2 and a review of Turkish foreign trade data from 2000 to 2020, the volume of trade conducted between Turkey and the MENA region significantly increased from \$8.78 billion in 2000 to \$62.02 billion in 2020, representing a growth of 606.00%. The year 2012 witnessed the highest volume of trade conducted between Turkey and the MENA region, reaching \$73.42 billion, which is an increase of 735.7% compared to 2000. Conversely, 2002 experienced the lowest trade volume during this period, amounting to \$7.52 billion, reflecting a decrease of 14.44% from 2000. Overall, from 2000 to 2020, the volume of trade conducted between Turkey and the MENA region demonstrated a general upward trend, with the exception of the decline observed in 2002 and 2009, peaking in 2012 before experiencing a downturn thereafter.

Table 3: Trade Transactions Between Turkey and the MENA Region (\$ bn) **Source:** based on WITS data

Year (1)	Trade Balance (2)	Export (3)	X (%) (4)	Import (5)	M (%) (6)	Trade Volume (7)	Annual change % (8)	Contribution % (9)	Change TV, % (10)	Importance (11)	base 2012 % (12)
2020	13,3	37,7	22,2	24,3	11,1	62,0	-1,7	15,9	606,0	5/7	-15,5
2019	24,1	43,6	24,1	19,5	9,3	63,1	0,4	16,1	618,2	4/7	-14,1
2018	16,9	39,9	22,5	23,0	9,9	62,8	-7,6	15,4	615,4	5/7	-14,4
2017	19,8	43,9	26,7	24,1	10,1	68,0	20,5	16,9	674,2	5/7	-7,4
2016	22,5	39,5	26,4	17,0	8,4	56,4	-1,6	16,1	542,4	5/7	-23,1
2015	23,4	40,4	26,7	17,0	8,0	57,4	-18,7	15,7	553,1	5/7	-21,9
2014	21,6	46,1	27,7	24,5	9,8	70,6	-2,6	16,9	703,1	5/7	-3,9
2013	20,4	46,4	28,7	26,0	10,0	72,4	-1,4	17,2	724,4	4/7	-1,4
2012	24,6	49,0	32,1	24,4	10,3	73,4	31,3	18,9	735,7	4/7	0,0
2011	8,9	32,4	24,0	23,5	9,8	55,9	26,6	14,9	536,4	5/7	
2010	12,6	28,4	24,9	15,8	8,5	44,2	29,1	14,8	402,7	5/7	
2009	16,0	25,1	24,6	9,1	6,4	34,2	-24,9	14,1	289,3	5/7	
2008	13,6	29,6	22,4	16,0	7,9	45,6	51,2	13,6	418,5	5/7	
2007	6,0	18,1	16,8	12,1	7,1	30,1	29,7	10,9	242,9	5/7	
2006	3,8	13,5	15,8	9,7	7,0	23,2	19,7	10,3	164,3	6/7	
2005	5,0	12,2	16,6	7,2	6,2	19,4	32,1	10,2	120,9	6/7	
2004	4,5	9,6	15,2	5,1	5,2	14,7	36,0	9,1	67,3	6/7	
2003	2,6	6,7	14,2	4,1	5,9	10,8	43,8	9,3	23,0	6/7	
2002	1,5	4,5	12,5	3,0	5,8	7,5	-16,9	8,6	-14,4	7/7	
2001	-0,8	4,1	13,1	4,9	11,9	9,0	2,9	12,4	2,9	2/7	
2000	-2,1	3,4	12,1	5,4	9,9	8,8	25,2	10,7	0,0		

Average trade balance over the period 2000-2020 12,3 (\$ billions)

Importance of the region in trade volume (2000-2020) 2/7

Importance of change in trade volume (2000-2020) by base year 2012 7/7

Average change in trade volume compared to 2012 -12,7 %

(4) MENA Share of exports (%)

(6) MENA share of imports (%)

(7) Türkiye trade volume with MENA

(8): Annual change in trade volume between MENA and Turkey %

(9) MENA contribution to Turkey's trade volume %

(10): Change in trade volume, base year 2000 %

(11): Importance of change in trade volume by base year 2000

(12): Change in trade volume, base year 2012 %

Figure 2: The Volume of Trade Conducted Between Turkey and the MENA Region. **Source:** based on WITS data.

4.5. Annual Variation in Trade Volume Between the MENA Region and Turkey

An analysis of the yearly fluctuations in the volume of Turkish trade with the MENA region reveals two distinct periods. The first period, from 2000 to 2012, exhibited predominantly positive growth, with the exceptions of 2002 and 2009, during which annual growth was negative. In contrast, the second period, from 2013 to 2020, consistently reflected negative growth, with only 2017 and 2019 showing positive annual growth.

Figure 3: Annual Variation in Trade Volume Between the MENA Region and Turkey. **Source:** based on WITS data.

4.6. The Significance of The MENA Region

The analysis of trade volumes between Turkey and various regions reveals that, while trade with the MENA region experienced remarkable growth of approximately 606% from 2000 to 2020, it consistently ranked second in terms of trade volume. In contrast, the Central Asia and Europe region maintained the top position throughout the study period.

Figure 4: Change in Volume of Trade Conducted Between Turkey and MENA Compared to the Year 2000. **Source:** based on WITS data.

In addition, while the trade exchange between Turkey and the MENA region experienced a significant increase of approximately 606% in 2020 compared to 2000, this figure places MENA fifth in terms of growth rate when compared to other regions. The highest growth rate was observed in trade exchange between Turkey and the South American and Caribbean region, which reached 1070.50%. The South Asian region followed in second place with a growth rate of 1010.07%, while sub-Saharan Africa ranked third at 947.13%. The Pacific and East Asia region were fourth with a growth rate of 640.84%. The MENA region came in fifth with 606%, whereas the Central Asia and Europe region and the North America region ranked sixth and seventh with growth rates of 298.26% and 217.86%, respectively, as depicted in Figure 5 and outlined in Table 4.

Table 4: Turkish foreign trade by region. **Source:** Based on WITS data

Partner Name	Year	Change in trade volume, base year 2000 %	Importance ranking by 2000 base year	Change in trade volume, base year 2010 %	Importance ranking by 2010 base year
World	2020	373,00%	*	29,97	*
ECA ²	2020	298,26%	6/7	22,57	7
EAP ³	2020	640,84%	4/7	32,34	5
MENA ⁴	2020	606,00%	5/7	40,45	3
LAC ⁵	2020	1070,50%	1/7	96,23	2
SSA ⁶	2020	947,13%	3/7	96,41	1
SA ⁷	2020	1010,07%	2/7	23,09	6
NA ⁸	2020	217,86%	7/7	36,08	4
World	2019	375,44%	*	30,64	*
ECA	2019	302,29%	6/7	23,81	7
EAP	2019	594,09%	5/7	23,99	6
MENA	2019	618,18%	4/7	42,87	4
NA	2019	213,21%	7/7	34,09	5
LAC	2019	1034,96%	2/7	90,28	1
SA	2019	1296,11%	1/7	54,81	3
SSA	2019	838,81%	3/7	76,09	2
World	2018	396,27%	*	36,37	*
ECA	2018	320,84%	6/7	29,52	7
EAP	2018	679,76%	4/7	39,29	6
MENA	2018	615,38%	5/7	42,31	5
NA	2018	239,23%	7/7	45,23	4
LAC	2018	1308,62%	2/7	136,16	1
SA	2018	1448,42%	1/7	71,70	3
SSA	2018	839,54%	3/7	76,23	2

Figure 5: Contribution of Regions to Turkey's Trade Volume in 2020 (%). **Source:** based on WITS data

4.7. The Impact of the MENA Region on Turkey's Trade Volume

The MENA region has significantly impacted Turkey's trade volume, with its contribution increasing from 10.68% in 2000 to 15.94% in 2020, representing an increase of 5.26%. Notably, the MENA region recorded its highest contribution to Turkey's trade volume in 2012 at 18.87%, while the lowest contribution occurred in 2002, at 8.58%. Upon analyzing Figure 6, it becomes clear that the MENA region's contribution to Turkish trade experienced an initial rise followed by a decline, after which it continued to increase, peaking in 2012 before experiencing another decrease, as illustrated in Figure 6 and Table 3.

Figure 6: Contribution of MENA to Turkey's Trade Volume. **Source:** based on WITS data.² Europe & Central Asia³ East Asia & Pacific⁴ Middle East & North Africa⁵ Latin America & Caribbean⁶ Sub-Saharan Africa⁷ South Asia⁸ North America

4.8. Variation in Trade Volume Relative to 2012

Following the change in the trade volume between Turkey and the MENA region, using 2012 as the base year, it is observed that from 2013 to 2020, the growth rate in trade volume compared to 2012 remained negative. Notably, the decrease reached -15.52% in 2020, with the most significant decline occurring in 2016 at -23.13%, while the smallest decrease was recorded in 2013 at -1.35%. Analyzing the overall trend in trade volume changes since 2012, there was a steady rise in the rate of decline from 2013 to 2016. Subsequently, there was a reduction in the rate of decline in 2017, followed by an increase in the decline once more in 2018. The rate of decline decreased slightly again in 2019, only to resume its upward trend in 2020, as shown in Figure 7 and Table 3.

Figure 7: Evolution of Trade Volume Between Turkey and the MENA Region Since 2012. **Source:** based on WITS data.

Figure 7 illustrates the fluctuations in the volume of trade exchange between Turkey and the MENA region since 2012. It is observed that trade exchange experienced a decline after 2012, reaching its lowest point in 2016. Subsequently, there was a modest recovery, followed by another decrease. During this entire period, trade volumes remained below the levels recorded in 2012.

During the period from 2013 to 2020, a comparison of the growth in Turkish trade with various geographical regions relative to 2012 reveals that the MENA region ranked seventh and last among these regions. The Latin American and Caribbean region exhibited the highest growth, with an average rate of 16.35%. The Pacific and East Asia region followed in second place, recording an average growth rate of 14.89%. Sub-Saharan Africa secured third place, boasting an average growth rate of 6.83%, while North America ranked fourth at 5.36%. South Asia came in fifth boasting an average growth rate of 5.25%, and Europe and Central Asia placed sixth boasting an average growth rate of 3.98%. Conversely, the MENA region experienced a decline, with a negative average growth rate of -12.70%. The average stands out as particularly noteworthy trade growth between Turkey and all regions, from 2013 to 2020 compared to 2012, was positive overall, apart from the exception of the MENA region, which saw a decrease in trade volume. This indicates an overall improvement in trade relations with other regions since 2012, with the MENA region being the only exception, as shown in Figure 8 and Table 5.

Figure 8: Average change in the volume of Turkey's trade with geographical regions over the period 2013-2020 compared with 2012. **Source:** based on WITS data.

Table 5. Turkish Trade by Geographical Region (\$ billions) **Source:** based on WITS data

Partner	Year	Turkey Trade Volume	Annual change in trade volume %	Regions' contribution %	Importance of the region	Change in trade volume, base year 2012 %	Importance ranking 2012 base	change TV compared 2012 (%) ⁹
World	2020	389,2	-0,5	100,0	-	0,04	-	-
ECA	2020	213,4	-1,0	54,8	1/7	2,3	5/7	4,0
EAP	2020	47,6	6,7	12,2	3/7	9,3	4/7	14,9
MENA	2020	62,0	-1,7	15,9	2/7	-15,5	7/7	-12,7
LAC	2020	10,4	3,1	2,7	5/7	28,9	1/7	16,4
SSA	2020	7,8	11,5	2,0	7/7	26,3	2/7	6,8
SA	2020	8,0	-20,5	0,0	6/7	-9,9	6/7	5,3
NA	2020	23,8	1,5	6,1	4/7	9,4	3/7	5,4
World	2019	391,2	-4,2	100,0	-	0,6	-	-
ECA	2019	215,6	-4,4	55,1	1/7	3,4	5/7	-
EAP	2019	44,6	-11,0	11,4	3/7	2,4	6/7	-
MENA	2019	63,1	0,4	16,1	2/7	-14,1	7/7	-
NA	2019	23,5	-7,7	6,0	4/7	7,8	4/7	-
LAC	2019	10,1	-19,4	2,6	6/7	25,0	1/7	-
SA	2019	10,1	-9,8	2,6	5/7	13,3	2/7	-
SSA	2019	7,0	-0,1	1,8	7/7	13,2	3/7	-
World	2018	408,3	1,3	100,0	-	5,0	-	-
ECA	2018	225,5	3,3	55,2	1/7	8,1	6/7	-
EAP	2018	50,1	-8,5	12,3	3/7	15,1	4/7	-
MENA	2018	62,8	-7,6	15,4	2/7	-14,4	7/7	-
NA	2018	25,4	2,0	6,2	4/7	16,8	3/7	-
LAC	2018	12,5	26,5	3,1	5/7	55,2	1/7	-
SA	2018	11,2	20,4	2,7	6/7	25,7	2/7	-
SSA	2018	7,0	4,0	1,7	7/7	13,3	5/7	-
World	2017	403,2	14,7	100,0	-	3,7	-	-
ECA	2017	218,3	12,6	54,2	1/7	4,7	6/7	-
EAP	2017	54,8	9,8	13,6	3/7	25,8	1/7	-
MENA	2017	68,0	20,5	16,9	2/7	-7,4	7/7	-
NA	2017	24,9	21,6	6,2	4/7	14,4	3/7	-
LAC	2017	9,9	32,6	2,5	5/7	22,7	2/7	-
SA	2017	9,3	9,2	2,3	6/7	4,5	5/7	-
SSA	2017	6,7	24,5	1,7	7/7	0,1	4/7	-
World	2016	351,4	-3,6	100,0	-	-9,7	-	-
ECA	2016	194,0	-4,5	55,2	1/7	-7,0	4/7	-
EAP	2016	49,9	0,6	14,2	3/7	14,6	1/7	-
MENA	2016	56,4	-1,6	16,1	2/7	-23,1	7/7	-
NA	2016	20,5	0,7	5,8	4/7	-5,9	3/7	-
SA	2016	8,5	1,0	2,4	5/7	-4,4	2/7	-
LAC	2016	7,5	1,7	2,1	6/7	-7,5	5/7	-
SSA	2016	5,4	-7,0	1,5	7/7	-12,6	6/7	-

4.9. Trade Balance

Between 2000 and 2020, Turkey consistently experienced a negative trade balance, indicating that the value of imports surpassed that of exports. An analysis of Turkey's trade balance with various geographical regions during this period reveals that the trade balance with the MENA represented the most favorable, recording an average surplus of 12.30 billion USD. Following this, the trade balance with Sub-Saharan Africa ranked second, with an average surplus of 0.73 billion USD. In third place was the trade balance with the Caribbean and Latin America, which experienced an average deficit of 2.24 billion USD. The trade balance with South Asia ranked fourth, with an average deficit of 3.53 billion USD. The trade balance with North America followed in fifth place, showing an average deficit of 4.17 billion USD, while the balance with the Pacific and East Asia reported a significant average deficit of 23.99 billion USD. Lastly, Turkey's trade balance with Europe and Central Asia recorded the largest average deficit of 26.18 billion USD.

It is noteworthy that despite the slower growth rates in commerce with the MENA, relative to other regions during this period, it nonetheless achieved the most favorable trade balance with a considerable surplus. This sharply contrasts with the significant deficits observed in other regions, except for Sub-Saharan Africa, which also recorded a small surplus. The data detailed in Table 6 and illustrated in Figure 9 provide an overview of the Turkish trade balance by region for the period from 2000 to 2020.

⁹ Average change in trade volume compared to 2012 (%)

Table 6: Turkish Trade by Geographical Region (\$ billions) **Source:** based on WITS data

Partner Name	Year	Trade Balance	Export	Export Partner Share (%)	Import	Import Partner Share (%)	Average trade balance 2000-2020
World	2020	-49,9	169,7	100	219,5	100	-54,6
ECA	2020	-11,5	101,0	59,5	112,5	51,2	-26,2
EAP	2020	-31,6	8,0	4,7	39,6	18,0	-24,0
MENA	2020	13,3	37,7	22,2	24,3	11,1	12,3
LAC	2020	-3,7	3,4	2,0	7,0	3,2	-2,2
SSA	2020	2,9	5,3	3,1	2,5	1,1	0,7
SA	2020	-3,6	2,2	1,3	5,8	2,6	-3,5
NA	2020	-1,4	11,2	6,6	12,6	5,7	-4,2
World	2019	-29,5	180,8	100	210,4	100	
ECA	2019	-1,7	107,0	59,2	108,6	51,6	
EAP	2019	-28,2	8,2	4,5	36,4	17,3	
MENA	2019	24,1	43,6	24,1	19,5	9,3	
NA	2019	-3,5	10,0	5,5	13,5	6,4	
LAC	2019	-3,0	3,6	2,0	6,5	3,1	
SA	2019	-5,1	2,5	1,4	7,6	3,6	
SSA	2019	3,5	5,2	2,9	1,7	0,8	
World	2018	-54,0	177,2	100	231,2	100	
ECA	2018	-12,3	106,6	60,2	118,9	51,4	
EAP	2018	-33,0	8,6	4,8	41,5	18,0	
MENA	2018	16,9	39,9	22,5	23,0	9,9	
NA	2018	-4,6	10,4	5,9	15,0	6,5	
LAC	2018	-5,5	3,5	2,0	9,0	3,9	
SA	2018	-6,0	2,6	1,5	8,6	3,7	
SSA	2018	2,2	4,6	2,6	2,4	1,0	
World	2017	-74,2	164,5	100	238,7	100	
ECA	2017	-31,2	93,6	56,9	124,8	52,3	
EAP	2017	-39,8	7,5	4,5	47,3	19,8	
MENA	2017	19,8	43,9	26,7	24,1	10,1	
NA	2017	-4,2	10,4	6,3	14,5	6,1	
LAC	2017	-4,8	2,5	1,5	7,4	3,1	
SA	2017	-5,5	1,9	1,1	7,4	3,1	
SSA	2017	0,9	3,8	2,3	2,9	1,2	
World	2016	-52,9	149,3	100	202,2	100	
ECA	2016	-18,8	87,6	58,7	106,4	52,6	
EAP	2016	-37,3	6,3	4,2	43,6	21,6	
MENA	2016	22,5	39,5	26,4	17,0	8,4	
NA	2016	-4,4	8,0	5,4	12,4	6,1	
SA	2016	-5,2	1,7	1,1	6,8	3,4	
LAC	2016	-3,5	2,0	1,3	5,5	2,7	
SSA	2016	1,2	3,3	2,2	2,1	1,0	

Figure 10: Average Turkish Trade Balance by Region for the Period 2000-2020. **Source:** based on WITS data.

4.10 Case Study of Key Nations Impacted by The Arab Spring Revolutions

An analysis of Table 7 provides insights into the trade exchanges between Turkey, along with several nations across the MENA, including Syria, Libya, Yemen, Tunisia, and Egypt. This analysis, in conjunction with political stability data, demonstrates that the trade dynamics between Turkey and these nations were affected to varying extents during the era of the Arab revolutions.

For example, in 2010, the volume of Turkish-Syrian trade reached \$2.5 billion, reflecting a notable increase. However, following the onset of the revolution in Syria in 2011, this figure declined to approximately \$1.94 billion and further decreased to \$0.56 billion in 2012, representing a reduction of 77%. While there was a temporary increase in trade volume in 2013 and 2014, the decline resumed and continued until the end of 2020. In subsequent years, trade volume began to increase again, yet it remained below the levels seen in 2010. This trend is clearly illustrated in Figure 10, which highlights the correlation between the decline in trade volume in 2011 and the significant deterioration in the political stability index for Syria during that same year.

Table 7: Trade Flows Between Turkey and Selected MENA Countries During the Arab Spring Period (100 million dollars)

Year	Syria		Tunisia		Libya		Yemen		Egypt	
	TF	PS	TF	PS	TF	PS	TF	PS	TF	PS
2000	7,3	40,21	2,27	59,79	8,82	34,92	0,7	14,29	5,16	47,62
2001	7,45	46,83	2,14	55,03	9,15	39,42	1	14,02	5,13	39,42
2002	7,73	53,44	1,93	50,26	9,19	43,92	1,2	13,76	4,45	31,22
2003	8,24	44,72	3,18	57,29	13,27	48,24	1,56	9,55	5,35	27,64
2004	7,51	35,92	3,56	50	18,51	58,25	2,05	6,31	7,28	21,36
2005	8,24	32,52	4,12	47,09	23,69	60,68	2	9,22	9,54	26,7
2006	7,97	35,75	4,75	52,66	27,87	55,56	1,98	12,08	11,02	22,22
2007	11,74	33,82	7,59	48,31	10,44	71,5	2,75	8,7	15,82	27,05
2008	17,54	31,73	11,43	48,08	14,11	74,04	3,54	2,88	23,69	28,85
2009	17,53	27,49	8,82	46,92	22,02	76,3	3,8	1,9	32,6	25,59
2010	25,07	22,27	9,94	43,6	23,58	47,39	3,31	1,9	31,77	19,43
2011	19,47	2,84	10,52	35,55	8,87	11,85	2,73	1,9	41,42	6,64
2012	5,65	0,47	9,92	22,27	25,56	6,64	4,86	1,42	50,21	7,58
2013	13,35	0,47	13,44	18,96	34,39	4,74	6,13	1,9	50,55	7,11
2014	24,8	0	11,81	18,57	24,25	4,29	6,63	0,95	49,78	7,62
2015	19,74	0	10,07	16,67	17,47	3,33	4,14	0,48	45,62	8,1
2016	18,88	0	11,59	11,43	11,75	3,81	5,46	0,48	42,77	9,05
2017	18,91	0,95	11,7	13,81	11,48	2,38	5,79	0	46	9
2018	18,92	0,94	11,93	16,98	19,55	1,89	7,42	0	54	12
2019	18,48	0,47	10,77	17,45	25,53	1,89	9,75	0	54	12
2020	18,42	0	10,79	25	33,27	2,36	8,42	0,94	48,59	11,79
2021	22,95	0,47	16,43	19,34	35,93	2,83	11,19	0,94	67,25	14,62
2022	24,69	0	19,47	24,53	36,08	4,25	11,23	1,42	71,07	14,62
2023	24,15	0	15,41	22,27	37,95	4,27	9,08	0,95	70	16,59

TF refers to trade flows, while PS denotes political stability. **Source:** Data from the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank.

Figure 10: Trade flows between Turkey and Syria during the Arab Spring (100 million dollars). Source: Data from the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank.

In 2010, the trade volume between Libya and Turkey amounted to approximately \$2.35 billion; however, this figure declined to \$0.88 billion in 2011, representing a decrease of 62%. This decline can be attributed to a notable deterioration in Libya's political stability during that period. Nevertheless, a significant recovery in trade volume was observed in 2012 and 2013. By the end of 2017, this upward trend faced another decline. Subsequently, the trade volume experienced further growth, surpassing pre-Arab Spring levels and reaching \$3.79 billion in 2023.

Figure 11: Trade flows between Turkey and Libya during the Arab Spring (100 million dollars). **Source:** Data from the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank.

In 2010, trade relations between Yemen and Turkey were valued at \$0.33 billion; however, this figure decreased to \$0.27 billion in 2011. Starting in 2012, there has been a renewed surge in trade volume, which reached \$1.12 billion in 2022. Current data suggests that the political stability in Yemen has not had a significant impact on trade exchanges with Turkey.

Figure 12: Trade flows between Turkey and Yemen during the Arab Spring (100 million dollars). **Source:** Data from the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank.

The trade relationship between Egypt and Turkey has experienced significant growth, despite the challenges to political stability in the region arising from the Arab Spring revolution. The trade volume rose from \$3.17 billion in 2010 to \$4.14 billion in 2011, ultimately reaching \$7 billion by 2023.

Figure 13. Trade flows between Turkey and Yemen during the Arab Spring (100 million dollars). **Source:** Data from the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank.

After analyzing the data pertaining to Tunisia, it is evident that the volume of Turkish-Tunisian trade experienced an increase following the outbreak of the Arab Spring revolutions in Tunisia, rising from 0.99 billion dollars in 2010 to 1.05 billion dollars in 2011. This trade volume, however, experienced a decline in 2012 and has since fluctuated, reaching \$1.94 billion in 2022. In 2023, the trade volume experienced a further reduction to \$1.54 billion. Notably, the political instability in Tunisia did not adversely affect trade flows with Turkey during the Arab Spring; in fact, despite a decline in Tunisia's political stability index from 43.6% to 35.55% globally from 2010 to 2011, a growth in commercial exchange between the two countries was recorded.

Figure 14: Trade flows between Turkey and Yemen during the Arab Spring (100 million dollars). **Source:** Data from the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank.

In analyzing the trade exchange between Turkey and the five countries, three key trends emerge. *The first trend* pertains to the nations directly influenced by the Arab Spring revolutions. In these countries, political stability has notably affected trade levels with Turkey. For instance, a decline in trade has been recorded in nations such as Syria and Libya. Although trade relations with Turkey initially deteriorated following the revolutions, there has been a subsequent upward trend. This assessment takes into account the enduring conflicts and instability, along with the significant damage sustained by infrastructure and the trade sector. *The second trend* highlights countries whose trade relations with Turkey have not been significantly impacted by the Arab Spring revolutions. These nations have generally maintained a steady upward trajectory; for example, Egypt and Tunisia may have navigated this situation due to the temporary effects of the revolutions. *The third trend* includes countries that experienced a minor decline in trade transactions, followed by a recovery to an upward trend. In this regard, Yemen serves as a pertinent example.

5. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS: MODEL, METHOD AND FINDINGS

In this research project, we selected 21 countries from the MENA region for an econometric analysis: Algeria, Bahrain, Syria, Tunisia, Lebanon, Libya, Iraq, Kuwait, Sudan, Saudi Arabia, Yemen, Qatar, Egypt, the United Arab Emirates, Jordan, Oman, Morocco, Mauritania, Israel, Iran, and Turkey. Our analysis encompasses data from the years 2000 to 2022. To investigate the impact of independent variables such as GDP, population size, political stability, trade volume, as well as geographical distance, we employed a gravity model utilizing analyze the dependent variable representing trade flows between Turkey and the MENA countries.

Data pertaining to GDP, population, political stability and Exchange Rate have been obtained from the World Bank's databases. Additionally, trade flow data between countries has been acquired from the International Monetary Fund's database, while distance data has been sourced from the CEPII institution's GeoDist database.

5.1. Model

The gravity model operates on the principle of Newton's law of gravitation, this concept suggests that the gravitational pull between two objects is proportional to the product of their masses and inversely proportional to the square of the distance between them. This concept was adapted for use in social sciences in the mid-19th century and later applied to the examination of global trade dynamics within the 1960s (Tatlıcı and Kızıltan, 2011, p. 288).

In 1962, Jan Tinbergen introduced a groundbreaking use of the gravity model to examine international trade dynamics, providing a quantitative framework for predicting bilateral trade volumes based on the gravity equation. According to this model, the scale of trade between two nations is largely determined by significant factors such as their respective Gross Domestic Products (GDPs) and their geographical proximity, paralleling the principles of Newtonian physics where gravitational forces depend on the masses of objects and the distances separating them. Tinbergen's fundamental principle emphasizes that the scale of trade between nations is primarily determined by the economic size of the trading partners, as reflected in their GDPs, while being inversely influenced by the geographical distance separating them. The fundamental equation of the model has been reformulated as follows (Borges Aguiar & Cossu, 2019: 294):

$$X_{ij} = \left(\beta_0 \frac{Y_i^{\beta_1} Y_j^{\beta_2}}{D_{ij}^{\beta_3}} \right) \quad (1)$$

X_{ij} : The trade flows between countries i and j

Y_i : GDP of the first country

Y_j : GDP of the second country

D : The distance separating countries i and j

β_0 : The gravitational constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2,$ and β_3 : Constants.

The development of gravity models began with Anderson's foundational study in 1979, which initiated theoretical examination and recognition of the model. Notably, the model gained significant prominence in the 2000s, primarily due to the contributions of Anderson and Van Wincoop in 2003. Their work underscored the gravity model's relevance in academic discourse and established it as a fundamental component of trade models (Bayar, 2014: 120-121).

To facilitate a more thorough analysis of trade flows, researchers have opted to enhance their model by integrating additional variables. In addition to the core factors, they have included independent variables such as shared borders, trade agreements, common languages, exchange rates, economic frameworks and alliances, historical ties, and political stability (Ibrahim, 2019: 67-68). By incorporating these elements, the gravitational model advances from its fundamental structure into a more comprehensive version that considers a wider array of influences stemming from these variables. This expanded model is developed through a transformation into logarithmic form to account for the variance in the units of the variables, as outlined below (Abdelkrim, 2016: 67).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Log}(T_{ijt}) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log(\text{GDP}_{it}) + \beta_2 \log(\text{GDP}_{jt}) + \beta_3 \log(\text{PCI}_{it}) + \\ & \beta_4 \log(\text{PCI}_{jt}) - \beta_5 \log(D_{ij}) + \beta_6 \log(P_{it}) + \beta_7 \log(P_{jt}) + \beta_8 \text{Border}_{ij} \\ & + \beta_9 \text{Language}_{ij} + \dots + \beta_k \text{Colonizer}_{ij} + \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

i : Represents the first country.

j : Represents the second country.

T_{ijt} : Refers to the total trade volume between countries i and j .

GDP_i : Measures the economic size of country i in terms of gross domestic product (GDP).

GDP_j : An indicator that defines the economic size of country j in terms of GDP.

PCI_i : A measure that expresses per capita GDP in country i .

PCI_j : A variable that indicates the per capita GDP of country j .

P_i : Refers to the total population of country i .

P_j : Indicates the total population of country j .

D_{ij} : Defines the geographical distance separating countries i and j , which is a variable that indirectly measures trade costs.

Border : It is a variable that expresses the existence of shared boundaries between the two countries; it takes a value of 1 if such a border exists and a value of 0 if it does not.

Language : A dummy variable based on whether the two countries share the same language; it is assigned a value of 1 if a common language exists and a value of 0 if it does not.

Colon : This variable reflects the existence of a historical connection or colonial relationship between the two countries. It is assigned a value of 1 when such a connection or relationship is present, and a value of 0 when it is not.

5.2. Method

The analysis was performed using a linear regression model with panel-corrected standard errors (PCSEs), which is an effective method for addressing correlations among panels in longitudinal data. The independent variables have been log-transformed, a standard practice in gravity models. Furthermore, we included essential economic variables such as GDP, population, distance, and trade volume, which enhance the model's accuracy. The estimated gravity model equation, utilizing the (PCSEs) method, is presented as follows:

$$\log t_t = \log gdp_i_t + \log gdp_j_t + \log pi_t + \log pj_t + \log psi_t + \log psj_t + \log exij_t + \log dij_t + aij_t + cbij_t + \delta_t + \eta_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

In the analysis, the following variables are defined:

$\log t_t$: represents the logarithm of the dependent variable that indicates trade flows between the two countries (i and j).

$\log(gdpi)$: denotes the logarithm of the (GDP) of the MENA countries.

$\log(gdpj)$: refers to the logarithm of the GDP of Turkey.

$\log(pi)$: is the logarithm of the population in the MENA countries.

$\log(pj)$: indicates the logarithm of the population of Turkey.

$\log(psi)$ is the logarithm of the political stability of the MENA countries

$\log(psj)$ is the logarithm of the political stability of Turkey.

$\log(dij)$: refers to the logarithm of distance between the two countries.

aij : Variable of trade agreements between Turkey and MENA countries.

$cbij$: Variable of common borders between Turkey and MENA countries.

δ_t : It refers to the specific, unobserved influences that remain unchanged over time.

η_i : Reflects a shared predictable pattern.

ε_{it} : is a random error term assumed to follow a normal distribution with identical properties and an expected value of zero, $E(\varepsilon_{it}) = 0$; $\text{Var}(\varepsilon_{it}) = \sigma^2 > 0$.

In this context, (β_0) denotes the constant of the equation, representing the baseline value when all independent variables are set to zero. The parameters ($\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8, \beta_9, \beta_{10}, \beta_{11}$) are the coefficients assigned to the independent variables.

5.3. Findings

According to PCSES model analysis, the estimation of sigma was calculated through casewise selection. Importantly, the analysis revealed no evidence of autocorrelation within the data. The Pseudo R^2 value obtained was 0.8349, indicating that the model explains approximately 83.49% pertaining to the variation in the dependent variable (t). This suggests a strong level of robustness and appropriateness of the model. Furthermore, the results of the Wald chi-squared test yielded a statistic of 7612.13, with a corresponding probability value ($\text{Prob} > \chi^2$) of 0.0000. These findings affirm the overall significance of the model, as the p-value is below the 0.05 threshold, demonstrating statistical significance. Furthermore, the majority of the coefficients demonstrated statistical significance, enhancing our confidence in the analysis. Below is an overview of the main results:

The constant term (intercept = -30.56419) represents the initial value of "t" when all other variables are held constant at zero. It is crucial to highlight that this term does not carry any direct economic significance.

The analysis demonstrates that the economic output (GDP) of nations in the MENA region positively influences trade flows (t) between Turkey and these countries. Specifically, the coefficient associated with the logarithm of GDP is 0.7925528, which is highly significant at the 99% confidence level, suggesting that a 1% rise in GDP correlates with an approximate 0.79% increase in trade flows (t). As GDP rises, these countries may enhance their capacity to produce goods and services domestically, potentially leading to increased trade with others. This finding highlights the importance of economic growth in MENA countries as a crucial factor in strengthening trade relations with Turkey. When the economies of these nations expand, their ability to import Turkish goods improves, alongside an increase in their exports to Turkey, thus promoting greater trade exchange between the two parties.

The analysis demonstrates a positive relationship between Turkey's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and trade flows with its trading partners. The estimated coefficient associated with the natural log of Turkey's GDP ($\log(\text{GDP}_j)$) is 0.3784415, which is highly significant at the 99% confidence level, indicating that a 1% increase in Turkey's GDP is associated with an approximate 0.37% increase in trade flows, holding other factors constant. These findings support the hypothesis that the growth of the Turkish economy not only expands the production

base but also enhances domestic demand, thereby facilitating foreign trade.

The logarithmic coefficient (π_i) for the the population in MENA region countries is 0.1609831, indicating a statistically significant positive relationship at a high confidence level of 99%. This suggests that a 1% increase in population is associated with a 0.16% increase in the dependent variable (t), assuming all other factors remain constant. The positive effect implies that trade flows between Turkey and countries with higher population density within the MENA region are likely to increase, potentially reflecting the influence of market size or local demand.

The logarithmic coefficient (π_j) representing the population of Turkey is 3.439049. This suggests that the growth of Turkey's population exerts a meaningful and beneficial impact on trade flows between Turkey and Countries across the Middle East and North Africa region, with a 99% confidence level. Specifically, a 1% increase in Turkey's population is associated with an approximate 3.43% increase in the dependent variable (t), assuming all other factors remain constant. This indicates that a growing population is correlated with rising demand for goods and services, which may enhance trade between these nations. Furthermore, the increasing population in Turkey may influence production dynamics, as a larger population could represent a broader market, potentially resulting in increased exports and imports.

Table 8: The Analysis by Using a Linear Regression Model with Panel-Corrected Standard Errors (PCSES)

Number of gaps in sample: 20						
Linear regression, correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs)						
Group variable:	id		Number of obs	=	448	
Time variable:	year		Number of groups	=	20	
Panels:	correlated (unbalanced)		Obs per group:			
Autocorrelation:	no autocorrelation		min	=	18	
Sigma computed by	casewise selection		avg	=	22.4	
			max	=	23	
Estimated covariances	=	210	R-squared	=	0.8349	
Estimated autocorrelations	=	0	Wald chi2(10)	=	7612.13	
Estimated coefficients	=	11	Prob > chi2	=	0.0000	
logt	Panel-corrected		z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
	Coef.	Std. Err.				
loggdp _i	.7925528	.0312475	25.36	0.000	.7313088	.8537968
loggdp _j	.3784415	.0644049	5.88	0.000	.2522103	.5046728
logpi	.1609831	.0158963	10.13	0.000	.1298269	.1921393
logpj	3.439049	.3332869	10.32	0.000	2.785819	4.092279
logpsi	-.0218867	.0289556	-0.76	0.450	-.0786387	.0348653
logpsj	.0755371	.0490521	1.54	0.124	-.0206032	.1716775
logex _{ij}	.0399782	.0099969	4.00	0.000	.0203845	.0595718
logdi _j	-.574335	.0411301	-13.96	0.000	-.6549486	-.4937214
ai _j	.0037849	.007888	0.48	0.631	-.0116753	.0192451
cbi _j	.1865547	.0411959	4.53	0.000	.1058122	.2672972
_cons	-30.56419	2.400486	-12.73	0.000	-35.26905	-25.85932

Source: Researchers based on the outputs of econometric analysis

The findings suggest that political stability in the MENA countries (PSI) has a statistically insignificant negative impact on trade flows (t). The estimated coefficient associated with the natural logarithm of the Political Stability Index (Log (PSI)) is -0.218867, indicating that a 1% rise in the Political Stability Index is associated with an approximate decrease in trade flows (t) of 0.21%, assuming all other factors remain constant. While this negative effect may seem counterintuitive initially, it can be contextualized by the prevailing political and economic environment in the region. In certain scenarios, higher political stability may result in protective policies or trade restrictions, thus constraining trade flows. Consequently, politically stable nations may place greater emphasis on their local economies, reducing their reliance on international trade. This underscores the necessity of examining the interplay between political stability and trade policies to gain a comprehensive understanding of the economic dynamics at play in the region.

The results indicate that political stability in Turkey (PSJ) has a statistically insignificant positive impact on trade flows (t). The estimated the factor associated with the natural logarithm of the Turkish political stability index (Log (PSJ)) is 0.755371, which suggests that a 1% increase in Turkey's political stability index is associated with an approximate 0.75% increase in trade flows (t), assuming other factors remain constant. This finding may imply that Turkey is perceived as a strategic trade hub between the Middle East and Europe. Its political stability bolsters its role as a trade bridge connecting these regions. Economic policies that prioritize political stability, such as enhancing infrastructure and facilitating cross-border trade, could be significant contributors to this positive effect.

The findings suggest that the exchange rate, as represented by the variable $\text{Log}(\text{ex}_{ij})$ -which measures the exchange rates of currencies in the MENA countries against the dollar, relative to the Turkish lira's exchange rate against the dollar- demonstrates a statistically meaningful positive effect on trade flows with a 99% confidence level. The estimated coefficient is 0.399782, this suggests that a 1% rise in the exchange rate index is associated with an approximate 0.39% increase in trade flows, assuming all other factors remain constant. This positive correlation highlights the influence of currency competitiveness on international trade. As MENA currencies strengthen relative to the Turkish lira (indicating a depreciation of the Turkish lira), Turkish exports become more affordable and appealing to importing nations within the region. Consequently, this scenario generates an increased demand for Turkish products, resulting in a growth in volume of intra-trade.

The findings indicate that the distance separating the two nations, represented by the variable $\text{Log}(\text{d}_{ij})$, exerts a negative influence on trade flows that is statistically significant at a 99% confidence level. The estimated coefficient of -0.574335, this suggests that a 1% rise in distance is associated with an approximate decrease in trade flows of 0.57%, assuming all other factors remain constant. This connection can be explained by the impact of distance on transportation and trade costs; as the distance between countries increases, so do shipping and distribution expenses, which subsequently leads to a reduction in trade volume. Furthermore, distance may also signify intangible barriers, such as cultural or linguistic differences, which can similarly impact trade dynamics.

The findings demonstrate that trade agreements between Turkey and countries in the MENA (represented by the variable aj) have a statistically insignificant positive effect on trade flows (t). The estimated coefficient is 0.0037849, suggests that a 1% rise in trade agreements correlates with an approximate 0.003% increase in trade flows, assuming other variables remain unchanged. This positive correlation between trade agreements and trade flows highlights the importance of these agreements in reducing trade barriers, such as tariffs and quotas, and in promoting economic cooperation among countries. Trade agreements establish a legal and regulatory framework that facilitates bilateral trade, leading to an increase in exports and imports between the involved parties. Turkey has established several trade arrangements involving nations across the Middle East and North Africa, such as free trade agreements and economic partnerships. These agreements play a vital role in stimulating trade by fostering a more stable and transparent environment, thereby encouraging both Turkish and foreign companies to broaden their business activities.

The findings reveal that the existence of common borders between two countries, as indicated by the variable cb_{ij} , demonstrates a significant positive effect on trade flows (t) with a 99% confidence level. The estimated coefficient of 0.1865547 suggests that the existence of common borders is associated with an approximate 0.18% increase in trade flows in comparison to countries without such borders. This finding supports the notion that the positive correlation between common borders and trade flows underscores the significance of geographic location and spatial proximity in facilitating international trade. Countries that share geographical boundaries often experience advantages such as reduced transportation costs, improved access to markets, and enhanced direct economic and trade connections.

6. RESULTS

During the period from 2000 to 2020, the trade volume between Turkey and the MENA region experienced significant growth, peaking in 2012. Although there was a subsequent decline, the trade volume has remained substantially higher compared to the levels recorded in 2000.

The trade relationship between Turkey and the MENA region has experienced significant growth, reaching nearly 606% in 2020 compared to the year 2000. However, during this period, the MENA region consistently ranked second in trade volume, following the Central Asia and Europe region, which maintained its position as the leading region throughout the study period.

The growth rate of trade volume between Turkey and the MENA region has remained comparatively lower than in other regions. In 2020, the MENA region ranked fifth in growth rate when analyzed against other regions since 2000.

The annual change in the trade volume between Turkey and the MENA region from 2000 to 2020 can be divided into two different categories periods. The first period, spanning from 2000 to 2012, experienced predominantly positive annual changes in trade volume, with the exceptions of 2002 and 2009, when negative growth occurred. In contrast, the second period, from 2013 to 2020, was marked by generally negative changes in trade volume, with positive growth recorded only in 2017 and 2019.

The MENA region has greatly contributed to the volume of Turkish foreign trade. Initially, this contribution experienced both an increase and a subsequent decline at the onset of the period in question. However, it continued to rise, peaking in 2012, before experiencing another decrease.

Between 2013 and 2020, the growth rate compared to 2012 consistently remained negative. In 2020, the decline reached 15.52%, with the most significant decrease occurring in 2016 at -23.13%. Overall, the trade exchange relative to 2012 experienced a decline, reaching its lowest point in 2016, followed by a modest improvement in 2017 before resuming its downward trend. However, it still remained below the levels recorded in 2012.

The MENA region ranks seventh and last in terms of percentage growth in the level of trade between Turkey and various regions of the world during the specified period 2013 to 2020, compared to 2012. This indicates a significant decrease in the importance of trade relations between Turkey and the MENA region, as well as a significant decrease in the volume of trade relative to other regions after 2012.

During the period from 2000 to 2020, the growth in trade volume with the MENA region was relatively low when compared to other geographical areas. However, the Turkish trade balance with the MENA region remained highly favorable, showing a significant surplus. In contrast, trade balances with other regions generally reflected deficits, excluding sub-Saharan Africa, which recorded a modest surplus, albeit substantially less than that with MENA region.

The MENA region has historically received limited attention, with the inaugural trade agreement between Turkey and MENA countries established in 1972. Following a period of minimal activity throughout the 1970s and 1980s, trade experienced a substantial surge agreement in the 1990s, peaking in the 2000s. While the number of trade agreements signed in the second decade showed a decline compared to the first decade, it remained above the levels recorded in the 1990s.

The limited number of trade and free trade agreements between Turkey and MENA countries, relative to the total count of MENA nations, indicates a need to initiate the signing of additional agreements to strengthen trade relations between the two regions.

The influence and consequences of the Arab Spring revolutions on trade relations with Turkey is influenced by the distinct circumstances of each country. In cases where revolutions concluded swiftly, such as in Egypt and Tunisia, trade exchanges have remained largely stable and have not suffered significant negative effects. Conversely, countries that underwent prolonged conflicts and were unable to achieve comprehensive political reconciliation with Turkey, such as Syria and Libya, have experienced detrimental outcomes in their trade relations. Conversely, nations like Yemen that have demonstrated political rapprochement have reaped the benefits of improved trade relations with Turkey.

The trade dynamics between Turkey and the nations of the MENA are shaped by several favorable factors, including GDP, population size, exchange rates, mutual trade agreements, and Turkey's political stability. Conversely, these trade flows encounter challenges related to the political instability in MENA countries, as well as the geographical distance separating Turkey from these nations. Most findings align with the gravity model; however, certain factors did not yield anticipated results, this might be attributed to the distinctive circumstances of these countries or the impact of unexamined variables.

Turkey's security, stability, and well-being are intrinsically connected to the security and stability of the MENA. Therefore, it is essential for Turkey and the nations within the region to demonstrate mutual support and solidarity in addressing various challenges. The most effective approach to overcoming these difficulties is through peaceful means, emphasizing coordination, cooperation, and dialogue.

In order to enhance the growth, success, and overall welfare of both the Turkish people and the wider region, Turkey should focus on strengthening engagement and cooperation with MENA countries across political, economic, social, and cultural domains. This effort should be guided by a framework of political and security stability that benefits all involved parties.

7. CONCLUSION

The Arab Spring revolutions, which began in late in 2010, it expanded throughout the MENA region, significantly impacted Turkey's trade relations with the region. A detailed analysis of these changes highlights a complex interaction of political, economic, and social factors that shaped Turkey's trading patterns with MENA countries during this tumultuous period.

Turkey's trade with the MENA region experienced significant growth prior to and shortly following the Arab Spring, driven by increasing economic integration and Turkey's strategic position as a key trade partner in the region. However, the consequences of the revolutions varied considerably among different countries. In Egypt

and Tunisia, where political transitions occurred relatively quickly and with a level of stability, trade relations proved resilient with only minor disruptions. Conversely, countries facing prolonged conflict and instability, such as Syria and Libya, saw a substantial decline in trade activities, highlighting the substantial effects of political turmoil and security concerns on economic interactions.

The Arab Spring emphasized the importance of political stability and bilateral relations in maintaining cross-border trade. Turkey aimed to leverage its economic influence and soft power to establish strong relationships with post-revolutionary governments. However, changing alliances and increasing geopolitical tensions sometimes hindered these initiatives. For instance, strained relations with certain MENA countries resulted in decreased trade volumes, illustrating the close interconnection between politics and economics in the region.

Throughout this challenging period, Turkey successfully sustained an overall trade surplus with the MENA region, thanks to its strong industrial base and favorable geographic position, which provided a competitive advantage. However, the slowdown in trade growth relative to other regions highlights the necessity for Turkey to implement a more proactive strategy for enhancing economic cooperation. Important initiatives may include expanding free trade agreements, fostering improved political dialogue, and addressing structural challenges such as geographic distance and regulatory discrepancies.

In conclusion, the Arab Spring represented a significant turning point in Turkey's trade relations with countries in the MENA region, highlighting both opportunities for collaboration and the vulnerabilities associated with political instability. While the revolutions created avenues for enhanced partnerships in certain areas, they also exposed the fragility of economic connections in times of conflict. Moving forward, it is essential for Turkey to focus on developing enduring and mutually beneficial partnerships with MENA states, grounded in shared goals of stability and prosperity. By strengthening its engagement across political, economic, and cultural dimensions, Turkey can not only enhance its trade relationships but also contribute positively to regional peace and sustainable development.

REFERANCES

- Abdelbaki, H. (2013). The impact of Arab spring on stock market performance. *British Journal of Economics, Management & Trade*, 3 (3), 169–185.
- Abdelkrim, E. (2016). *Using gravity modeling to estimate the trade potential of Maghreb countries: Algeria, Tunisia and Morocco* (Doctoral dissertation, Hassiba Ben Bouali University of Chlef, Department of Economics).
- Abdelmeguid, M. S., & Al Haiti, M. A. A. (2020). The Arab Spring revolutions and the social dimensions of development policies: The Egyptian case. *Annals of Arts and Social Sciences*, 40 (543), 9–143.
- AlShammari, N., Willoughby, J., & Behbehani, M. S. (2023). Political unrest, the Arab Spring, and FDI flows: A quantitative investigation. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11 (2), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2176281>
- Arayssi, M., Fakih, A., & Haimoun, N. (2019). Did the Arab Spring reduce MENA countries' growth? *Applied Economics Letters*, 26 (19), 1579–1585. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2018.1545964>
- Ardıç, N. (2012). Understanding the 'Arab Spring': Justice, dignity, religion and international politics. *Afro Eurasian Studies*, 1 (1), 8–52.
- Bayar, G. (2014). Türkiye'nin Kalkınmış Ülkelere ve Orta Doğu-Kuzey Afrika Ülkelerine İhracatı: Karşılaştırmalı Yer Çekimi Analizi. *Yakın Doğu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 7 (2), 119–164.
- Borges Aguiar, G. M., & Cossu, E. (2019). The gravity model for trade theory. *Köz-gazdaság*, 14 (3), 293–299.
- Button, K., Martini, G., & Scotti, D. (2016). Impacts of the Arab Spring on trade in airline services. *Applied Economics Letters*, 23 (7), 532–535. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2015.1072923>
- Campante, F. R., & Chor, D. (2012). Why was the Arab world poised for revolution? Schooling, economic opportunities, and the Arab Spring. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 26 (2), 167–188. <https://www.aeaweb.org/articles?id=10.1257/jep.26.2.167>
- Davutoğlu, A. (2008). Turkey's Foreign Policy Vision: An Assessment of 2007. *Insight Turkey*, 10 (1), 77–96.
- Davutoğlu, A. (2012a), Turkey's Foreign Policy Objectives in a Changing World [Speech]. Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), Washington D.C. Quoted in Fahrettin Sümer, "Turkey's Changing Foreign Policy and the Arab uprisings". *The Innovation Journal*, 18 (1).

- Davutoğlu, A. (2012b), Interview by Mr. Ahmet Davutoğlu published in AUC Cairo Review (Egypt) on 12 March 2012. Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Republic of Türkiye. https://www.mfa.gov.tr/interview-by-mr_-ahmet-davuto%C4%9Flu-published-in-auc-cairo-review-_egypt_-on-12-march-2012.en.mfa
- Echevarría, C. A., & García-Enríquez, J. (2020). The economic cost of the Arab Spring: The case of the Egyptian revolution. *Empirical Economics*, 59, 1453–1477. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-019-01724-y>
- El Faith, A. (2015). The Arab Spring: Its origins, evolution and consequences... four years on. *Intellectual Discourse*, 23 (1), 119–139.
- Falk, R. (2012, February 9). Turkey's Foreign Policy: Zero Problems with Neighbors Revisited. *Foreign Policy Journal*. <https://www.foreignpolicyjournal.com/2012/02/09/turkeys-foreign-policy-zero-problems-with-neighbors-revisited/>
- Hacıoğlu, N., & Saylan, U. (2014). Arap Baharı'nın Turizme Yansımaları: Arap Ülkeleri ve Türkiye. *Balkesir Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 17 (32), 55–80.
- Hraiba, A., Ganić, M., & Branković, A. (2019). Does the Arab spring wave affect outward Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)? Empirical evidence from the Mideast and North Africa. *Ekonomski Pregled*, 70 (3), 411–430.
- Ibrahim, W. (2019). Trade Flows between Egypt and COMESA Countries Gravity Model. *Journal of the Faculty of Economics and Political Science*, 20 (2), 61–88.
- Jeniček, V., & Krepl, V. (2009). The role of foreign trade and its effects. *Agricultural Economics*, 55 (5), 211–220.
- Kahveci, M. (2019). From Spring to Winter? An Analysis of "Arab Spring" Impacts on Turkey and MENA Region Foreign Trade with Gravity Approach. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 9 (12), 1320–1334.
- Khan, M. (2014). *The Economic Consequences of the Arab Spring*. Rafik Hariri Center for the Middle East. https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/177370/The_Economic_Consequences_of_the_Arab_Spring.pdf
- Karim, E. (2021). *Economic Consequences of the Arab Spring in The Middle East* (Doctoral thesis, Seoul National University Graduate School). https://dcollection.snu.ac.kr/public_resource/pdf/000000166831_20250126204347.pdf
- Kırşanlı, F. (2023). Corruption and economic growth nexus: what has the Arab spring changed? *Current Research in Social Sciences*, 9 (1), 41–57.
- Legamart. (n.d.). *What is Turkey Foreign Trade Policy?* <https://legamart.com/articles/what-is-turkey-foreign-trade-policy/>
- Matta, S., Appleton, S., & Bleaney, M. (2016). The impact of the Arab Spring on the Tunisian economy (World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 7856). World Bank.
- Öncel, A., & Malik, A. (2015). The Arab Spring and its impact on the foreign trade of Turkey. *Bilgi Derig*, (1), 17–36.
- Paul, A., & Seyrek, D. (2011, July 15). Turkish foreign policy and the Arab Spring [Commentary]. European Policy Center. https://www.files.ethz.ch/isn/141519/pub_1322_turkish_foreign_policy_and_the_arab_spring.pdf
- Republic of Türkiye, Ministry of Foreign Affairs. (n.d.). Turkey's Relations with the Arab Countries. https://www.mfa.gov.tr/turkiye_s-relations-with-the-arab-countries.en.mfa
- Sen, A., El-Anis, I., & Saray, O. (2016). The Growing Interest of Turkey in the Middle East and North Africa: A new approach or business as usual? https://irep.ntu.ac.uk/id/eprint/27863/1/PubSub5367_El-Anis.pdf
- Tatlıcı, Ö., & Kızıltan, A. (2011). Çekim Modeli: Türkiye'nin İhracatı Üzerine Bir Uygulama. *Atatürk Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 25, 287–299.
- TCTB [Turkish Ministry of Trade]. (n.d.). <https://ticaret.gov.tr/>
- Veninga, W., & Ihle, R. (2018). Import vulnerability in the Middle East: Effects of the Arab spring on Egyptian wheat trade. *Food Security*, 10, 183–194. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-017-0762-z>
- World Bank. (n.d.). *World Development Indicators*, <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators#>
- WITS – World Integrated Trade Solution. (n.d.). <https://wits.worldbank.org/CountryProfile/en/Country/TUR/year/LTST/TradeFlow/Export202>